

Analysis and Design of Periodic Multi-Element mmWave Metasurfaces by a Fast Extended Method-of-Lines Formulation

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We introduce a method-of-lines (MoL) formulation for analyzing and designing periodic multi-element millimeter-wave (mmWave) metasurfaces (MSs) in a computationally tractable manner. As the complexity of MSs increases, their analysis and especially their design using full-wave methods becomes challenging. MoL offers a considerably faster alternative, as it is a semi-analytical method where the electromagnetic equations are solved analytically along the direction perpendicular to the MS layers and numerically on the MS plane; hence, the required degrees of freedom (DoFs) are substantially decreased. We employ an extended MoL formulation, where a first-order differential equation involving both the total tangential electric and magnetic field components is solved, and the transfer matrix of each layer is obtained. As a proof of concept, we analyze various MS filter supercells, varying the polarization of the incident wave and the resonator parameters. A very good agreement with finite-element method (FEM) simulations is observed in all cases. By comparing the extended MoL to the FEM in terms of computational requirements, we verify that MoL presents a considerably faster alternative for MS design. The presented analysis paves the way for the fast synthesis of optimized MSs by changing only the boundary conditions (BCs) on the layer interfaces. The advantages of our method will be even more pronounced in the design of even more complex devices.

Index Terms—Computational electromagnetics, electromagnetic metamaterials, metasurfaces (MSs), millimeter-wave (mmWave) devices, periodic structures.

I. INTRODUCTION

METASURFACES (MSs) are the 2-D extension of metamaterials and are artificial materials that control propagating waves. They function as absorbers [1], gratings and antennas [2]. Advanced functionalities can be achieved by multi-layer [1], [3] or periodic multi-element MSs [3], which provide increased degrees of freedom (DoFs). The analysis and design of MSs is carried out in most cases by full-wave methods, such as the finite-element method (FEM) [4], method of moments (MoMs) [5], and finite-difference frequency domain (FDFD). Although full-wave methods provide highly accurate results, they become computationally challenging as the complexity and size of the MSs increase. Hence, there is a need for faster and computationally tractable methodologies to facilitate fast metasurface synthesis.

Analytical or semi-analytical approaches can be used as alternatives to the full-wave methods for faster analysis and design. Equivalent circuit approaches can be used to some extent to model MS [6]; however, it is challenging to derive accurate equivalent circuit models for MS with complex resonator patterns. The characteristic-mode analysis has also been used to guide the synthesis of broadband metasurface absorbers [2] and antennas [7] and to provide physical insight; however, it cannot be used to calculate the metasurface response. Semi-analytical methods, such

as temporal coupled-mode theory, have also been used to analyze complex MS [8], [9]; however, the method is only applicable to weakly coupled resonators. Hence, there is a need for alternative, versatile semi-analytical approaches that can be used to analyze a variety of MS devices.

The method of line (MoL) [10] presents a favorable alternative; it is a semi-analytical method, where the wave equations are solved analytically along the direction perpendicular to the MS and numerically on the MS plane, eliminating the need to discretize the entire 3-D domain. The decoupled wave equations are commonly solved for the transverse electric or magnetic field components, with the field components at each layer expressed in terms of the forward and backward propagating waves. This approach has been used in graphene-based structures—flat [11], [12] or curvilinear [13], and multi-layer dielectric MSs [14], [15]. However, non-uniform periodic multi-element millimeter-wave (mmWave) MSs with metal patterns have not been considered. A more general extended formulation [16], [17] has also been introduced, which is applicable to any medium, even bianisotropic, where electric and magnetic fields cannot be decoupled. The extended MoL solves a first-order differential equation that involves both the electric and magnetic tangential field components; the transfer matrix of each layer is obtained. Extended MoL applications are rather limited, mostly to transmission line components [17] and conformal antennas [16].

In this article, we introduce a fast and computationally tractable MoL formulation, based on a first-order differential equation, to analyze and design periodic multi-element mmWave MSs, comprised of more than one resonator type. Such periodic non-uniform MSs can achieve increased

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Fig. 1. (a) MS unit cell placed on the $z = 0$ plane excited by an incident plane wave along the z -axis. (b) Yee cell is adopted across the xy plane.

functionalities compared with uniform MSs; hence, a fast method for their synthesis is required. Our main contribution is that we introduce the metal resonator patterns as a surface current density boundary condition (SCDBC), which greatly facilitates and expedites the synthesis process. The transfer matrices of each dielectric substrate are computed only once per frequency, which constitutes the primary computational cost. The transfer matrix for the entire device is simply obtained by multiplying the transfer matrices of each dielectric layer. Boundary conditions (BCs), including the metal pattern's SCDBC, are then seamlessly imposed between dielectric interfaces when forming the transfer matrix of the entire device. As a proof of concept, we analyze periodic multi-element MS filters by the proposed MoL formulation. A very good agreement between the MoL and FEM simulations is observed in all cases. We also demonstrate the advantages of our approach by varying the MS's metal structure parameters as well as the polarization of the incident wave, both of which are common steps in designing MSs of a desired functionality. We show that although the FEM would require the simulation of the entire MS when changing a single design parameter, in the proposed MoL formulation, we only change the cells where the SCDBCs are imposed and calculate the final transfer matrix. The advantages of the extended MoL will become more pronounced in the design of even more complex MSs.

II. EXTENDED MoL FORMULATION

A. Formulation

The MoL formulation employs Maxwell's normalized equations expressed in terms of the tangential electric and magnetic field intensity components. Throughout this article, we consider MSs that are placed on the xy plane and are excited by an incident plane wave along the z -axis. Fig. 1(a) shows the adopted axes convention. Hence, the tangential electric and magnetic field components are E_x , E_y , H_x , and H_y . Our derivation begins from Maxwell's equations

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -j\omega\mu\mathbf{H}, \quad \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = j\omega\epsilon\mathbf{E}. \quad (1)$$

To obtain Maxwell's normalized equations, as is common in MoL formulations [10], the coordinates x , y , and z are replaced by $x' = k_0x$, $y' = k_0y$, and $z' = k_0z$, and the magnetic field component intensities $[\tilde{H}_x, \tilde{H}_y, \tilde{H}_z]$ by $\tilde{H}_x = Z_0 H_x$, $\tilde{H}_y = Z_0 H_y$, and $\tilde{H}_z = Z_0 H_z$. The normalized

equations are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y'} &= j\tilde{H}_x, & \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x'} &= -j\tilde{H}_y \\ \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x'} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y'} &= -j\tilde{H}_z, & \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_y}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_z}{\partial y'} &= -j\epsilon_r E_x \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_x}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_z}{\partial x'} &= j\epsilon_r E_y, & \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_y}{\partial x'} - \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_x}{\partial y'} &= j\epsilon_r E_z. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

By substituting the longitudinal components E_z and \tilde{H}_z with the transverse ones, we derive the following equations that are expressed only in terms of the transverse electric and magnetic field intensity components. These equations are used for the MoL formulation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z'} &= -j\tilde{H}_y - \frac{j}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{H}_y}{\partial x'^2} + \frac{j}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{H}_x}{\partial x' \partial y'} \\ \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z'} &= +j\tilde{H}_x + \frac{j}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{H}_x}{\partial y'^2} - \frac{j}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{H}_y}{\partial y' \partial x'} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_x}{\partial z'} &= +j\epsilon_r E_y + j \frac{\partial^2 E_y}{\partial x'^2} - j \frac{\partial^2 E_x}{\partial x' \partial y'} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_y}{\partial z'} &= -j\epsilon_r E_x - j \frac{\partial^2 E_x}{\partial y'^2} + j \frac{\partial^2 E_y}{\partial y' \partial x'}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

B. Discretization

A 2-D discretization scheme based on the Yee cell [18] is considered at the xy plane. The size of the grid is $N_x \times N_y$, with N_x and N_y being the number of cells along the x - and y -axes, and Δ_x and Δ_y being the corresponding cell size. The cell size is set to be considerably subwavelength to ensure satisfactory accuracy of the MoL. In all examples of this article, we set the grid size to $\Delta_x = \Delta_y = 0.12$ mm, which corresponds to about 1/60 of the free space wavelength at the highest frequency of 40 GHz. Then, $N_{x/y} = p_{x/y}/\Delta_{x/y}$, where $p_{x/y}$ is the MS period along each axis. The components E_x and \tilde{H}_y are co-located, as are E_y and \tilde{H}_x . The adopted Yee cell is shown in Fig. 1(b) for the cell (i, j) . Periodic BCs (PBCs) are imposed along the x - and y -axes. They are introduced into the system equations, as they hold for any z . Metal surfaces are only applicable to certain z planes and therefore will be imposed as BCs in the next step. The discretized form of the normalized (3) is provided in (4) for the components $E_x^{i,j}$, $E_y^{i,j}$, $\tilde{H}_x^{i,j}$, and $\tilde{H}_y^{i,j}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial E_x^{i,j}}{\partial z'} &= -j\tilde{H}_y^{i,j} - j \frac{1}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\tilde{H}_y^{i+1,j} - 2\tilde{H}_y^{i,j} + \tilde{H}_y^{i-1,j}}{\Delta x'^2} \\ &\quad + j \frac{1}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\tilde{H}_x^{i+1,j} - \tilde{H}_x^{i+1,j-1} - \tilde{H}_x^{i,j} + \tilde{H}_x^{i,j-1}}{\Delta x' \Delta y'} \\ \frac{\partial E_y^{i,j}}{\partial z'} &= j\tilde{H}_x^{i,j} + j \frac{1}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\tilde{H}_x^{i,j+1} - 2\tilde{H}_x^{i,j} + \tilde{H}_x^{i,j-1}}{\Delta y'^2} \\ &\quad - j \frac{1}{\epsilon_r} \frac{\tilde{H}_y^{i,j+1} - \tilde{H}_y^{i-1,j+1} - \tilde{H}_y^{i,j} + \tilde{H}_y^{i-1,j}}{\Delta x' \Delta y'} \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{H}_x^{i,j}}{\partial z'} &= j\epsilon_r E_y^{i,j} + j \frac{E_y^{i+1,j} - 2E_y^{i,j} + E_y^{i-1,j}}{\Delta x'^2} \\ &\quad - j \frac{E_x^{i,j+1} - E_x^{i-1,j+1} - E_x^{i,j} + E_x^{i-1,j}}{\Delta x' \Delta y'} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{H}_y^{i,j}}{\partial z'} = -j\epsilon_r E_x^{i,j} - j \frac{E_x^{i,j+1} - 2E_x^{i,j} + E_x^{i,j-1}}{\Delta y'^2} + j \frac{E_y^{i+1,j} - E_y^{i+1,j-1} - E_y^{i,j} + E_y^{i,j-1}}{\Delta x' \Delta y'}. \quad (4)$$

The matrix form of (4) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_x}{\partial z'} &= -j\mathbf{M}_{xy}\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y + 1\frac{1}{\epsilon}\mathbf{P}_{xx}\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_y}{\partial z'} &= j\mathbf{M}_{yx}\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x - 1\frac{1}{\epsilon}\mathbf{P}_{yy}\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x}{\partial z'} &= j\mathbf{N}_{xy}\mathbf{E}_y + 1\frac{1}{\mu}\mathbf{Q}_{xx}\mathbf{E}_x \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y}{\partial z'} &= -j\mathbf{N}_{yx}\mathbf{E}_x + 1\frac{1}{\mu}\mathbf{Q}_{yy}\mathbf{E}_y. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) can be written in the following form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x \\ \mathbf{E}_y \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y \end{bmatrix} = j\mathbf{A}_s \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x \\ \mathbf{E}_y \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{A}_s = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{Z} \\ \mathbf{Y} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

and the matrices \mathbf{Z} and \mathbf{Y} are expressed in terms of the matrices \mathbf{M}_{xy} , \mathbf{P}_{xx} , \mathbf{M}_{yx} , \mathbf{P}_{yy} , \mathbf{N}_{xy} , \mathbf{Q}_{xx} , \mathbf{N}_{yx} , and \mathbf{Q}_{yy}

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} j\mathbf{P}_{xx} & -j\mathbf{M}_{xy} \\ j\mathbf{M}_{yx} & -j\mathbf{P}_{yy} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} -j\mathbf{Q}_{xx} & j\mathbf{N}_{xy} \\ -j\mathbf{N}_{yx} & j\mathbf{Q}_{yy} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

The solution to the first-order differential equation of (6) is a matrix exponential

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(z'_1) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(z'_1) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z'_1) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z'_1) \end{bmatrix} = e^{\mathbf{A}_s(z'_1 - z'_2)} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(z'_2) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(z'_2) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z'_2) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z'_2) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The term $\mathbf{T} = e^{\mathbf{A}_s(z'_1 - z'_2)} = e^{\mathbf{A}_s k_0(z_1 - z_2)}$ is the $ABCD$ matrix [19], $\mathbf{E}_x(z'_1)$, $\mathbf{E}_y(z'_1)$, $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z'_1)$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z'_1)$ are the tangential field components on the $z = z_1$ plane, and $\mathbf{E}_x(z'_2)$, $\mathbf{E}_y(z'_2)$, $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z'_2)$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z'_2)$ on the $z = z_2$ plane. By multiplying the $ABCD$ matrices of consecutive layers and applying suitable BCs on the interfaces, we obtain the transfer matrix of the entire device.

C. Boundary Conditions

1) *Continuity BC*: In the absence of metal, continuity BCs are applied to the tangential electric and magnetic field components $\mathbf{E}_t/\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_t^{z^+} = \mathbf{E}_t/\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_t^{z^-}$. For the example of Fig. 1(a), the input $[\mathbf{E}(0^-), \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(0^-)]$ and the output $[\mathbf{E}(h^-), \tilde{\mathbf{H}}(h^-)]$ transverse field components are straightforwardly connected

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(0^-) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(0^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(0^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(0^-) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(0^+) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(0^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(0^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(0^+) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(h^-) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(h^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(h^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(h^-) \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{T} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(h^+) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(h^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(h^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(h^+) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

2) *Surface Current Density BC*: Conductive inks, which have surface resistance R_s , have recently been used as metal surfaces, especially in flexible and conformal MSs. Metal surfaces can be modeled by an SCDBC

$$\hat{n} \times (\mathbf{H}^+ - \mathbf{H}^-) = \sigma \mathbf{E}_t \quad (10)$$

with $\sigma = 1/R_s$. By imposing SCDBC on the interface between layers, we assume continuity of the tangential electric field components $\mathbf{E}_t^+ = \mathbf{E}_t^-$, and relate the tangential magnetic field intensity components on both sides through (10). The SCDBC is decomposed into

$$\mathbf{H}_y^{z^+} = \mathbf{H}_y^{z^-} - \sigma \mathbf{E}_x^z, \quad \mathbf{H}_x^{z^+} = \mathbf{H}_x^{z^-} + \sigma \mathbf{E}_y^z. \quad (11)$$

We express the SCDBC in terms of the normalized tangential magnetic field intensity components $\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_t$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y^{z^+} = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y^{z^-} - \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{E}_x^z, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x^{z^+} = \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x^{z^-} + \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{E}_y^z. \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) along with the continuity BCs in terms of the tangential electric field components can be written in the following form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(z^-) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(z^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z^-) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(z^+) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(z^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z^+) - \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{E}_y(z^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z^+) + \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{E}_x(z^+) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

For the example of Fig. 1(a), where metal cells lie on the $z = 0$ plane, we propagate all components to the $z = 0$ plane. Continuity BCs are imposed on the $z = h$ plane. For the metal surfaces that lie on the $z = 0$ plane, (13) is written as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(0^-) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(0^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(0^-) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(0^-) \end{bmatrix} = \{\mathbf{T} + \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{T}_m\} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(h^+) \\ \mathbf{E}_y(h^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(h^+) \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(h^+) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{T}_{ij} is the (i, j) block of \mathbf{T} , with \mathbf{T} partitioned into a 4×4 grid of submatrices. The matrix \mathbf{T}_m is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{T}_m = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ -\mathbf{T}_{21} & -\mathbf{T}_{22} & -\mathbf{T}_{23} & -\mathbf{T}_{24} \\ \mathbf{T}_{11} & \mathbf{T}_{12} & \mathbf{T}_{13} & \mathbf{T}_{14} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

D. S-Parameter Calculation

By multiplying the $ABCD$ matrices of all consecutive layers and imposing suitable BCs between the dielectric interfaces, we obtain the total $ABCD$ matrix, which connects the tangential fields on the lower part of the device to those of the upper part of the device. We must then transform the $ABCD$ matrix into the S -parameters following the process described for the existing MoL formulation [20]. For the latter step, we utilize the second-order differential equation in terms of the electric field, as the device will always reside in air; hence, there is no need for a general formulation that can potentially incorporate even bianisotropic media

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z'^2} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x \\ \mathbf{E}_y \end{bmatrix} - \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Y} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x \\ \mathbf{E}_y \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (16)$$

We calculate the eigenvalues λ^2 and the eigenvectors \mathbf{W} of the matrix \mathbf{ZY} . The electric and magnetic field intensity components at a layer z are calculated as follows [20]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_x(z') \\ \mathbf{E}_y(z') \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_x(z') \\ \tilde{\mathbf{H}}_y(z') \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} \\ -\mathbf{V} & \mathbf{V} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e^{-\lambda z'} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & e^{\lambda z'} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}^+ \\ \mathbf{c}^- \end{bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

with $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{Y}\mathbf{W}\lambda^{-1}$. The terms $e^{-\lambda z'}$ and $e^{\lambda z'}$ describe the forward and backward propagation through the layer, \mathbf{c}^+ and \mathbf{c}^- are amplitude coefficients of the eigenmodes in the forward and backward directions. By combining (17) and (14), the following equation relates the output and input amplitude coefficients:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} \\ -\mathbf{V} & \mathbf{V} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_i^+ \\ \mathbf{c}_i^- \end{bmatrix} = \{\mathbf{T} + \sigma Z_0 \mathbf{T}_m\} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{W} & \mathbf{W} \\ -\mathbf{V} & \mathbf{V} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_o^+ \\ \mathbf{c}_o^- \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

We then rearrange (18) into a form that resembles the S -parameter matrix. We note that (18) only resembles the S -parameter matrix, since it relates the coefficients \mathbf{c} instead of the field components

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_i^- \\ \mathbf{c}_o^+ \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{S}_{11,c} & \mathbf{S}_{12,c} \\ \mathbf{S}_{21,c} & \mathbf{S}_{22,c} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}_i^+ \\ \mathbf{c}_o^- \end{bmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

The reflected electric field \mathbf{E}_r and the transmitted electric field \mathbf{E}_t are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_r^x \\ \mathbf{E}_r^y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{S}_{11,c}\mathbf{W}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E}_t^x \\ \mathbf{E}_t^y \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{W}\mathbf{S}_{21,c}\mathbf{W}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{1} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

for an x -polarized incident plane wave. For a y -polarized incident plane wave, the last vector would be $\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{1} \end{bmatrix}$. Once we have obtained the reflected and transmitted tangential electric field at all DoFs, we calculate the corresponding fields at the center of each cell. Finally, the reflection and transmission coefficients are calculated as the fraction of the total reflected/transmitted wave to the incident wave

$$S_{ij}^{x/y,x/y} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_x N_y} \mathbf{E}_{x/y,n}^{r/t} \Delta_x \Delta_y}{\sum_{n=1}^{N_x N_y} \Delta_x \Delta_y}. \quad (21)$$

III. ANALYSIS AND DESIGN OF MS FILTERS

A. Periodic Uniform MS Filter

We apply the extended MoL formulation to a ring-resonator MS unit cell. A metal ring resonator is arranged on the top plane of a dielectric substrate and is shown as an inset of Fig. 2(a). This uniform MS has a period $p = 2.88$ mm, ring resonator of size $R_1 = 2.64$ mm, width $w = 0.24$ mm, $R_s = 0.01$ Ω/sq , and the dielectric substrate has a relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 2.2 - j0.0022$ and thickness $h = 0.8001$ mm. We compare the S -parameter magnitude [see Fig. 2(a)] and phase [see Fig. 2(b)] obtained by the extended MoL and the FEM; an excellent agreement is observed, with the average absolute error $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0106$ for the $|S_{21}|$ and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0028$ for the $|S_{11}|$. We consider $N_x = 24$ and $N_y = 24$ grid points along the x - and y -axes, with the total grid size being $24 \times 24 = 576$. The DoFs used in the MoL formulation are $4 \times N_x \times N_y = 2304$, while 1442902 DoFs are needed

Fig. 2. (a) Magnitude and (b) Phase of the S -parameters calculated both by the extended MoL (M.) and FEM (F.) for the MS filter shown as an inset.

for FEM. The FEM takes about 18 min per frequency on an Intel Xeon Gold 5120 system (14 cores, 28 threads, 2.20 GHz, DDR4-2400) and 3 min on an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3960X system (24 cores, 48 threads, 3.80 GHz, DDR4-3200), whereas the MoL takes about 7 s on the Intel and 6 s on the AMD machines.

B. Multi-Element Metasurface Filters

We investigate 2×1 periodic multi-element MS supercells of size $2p \times p$ that consist of two types of ring resonators with sizes R_1 and R_2 . They are placed on the top of the substrate at $x = p/2$ and $x = 3p/2$, as shown in Fig. 3(a), with the same substrate properties and R_s as in the uniform MS.

1) *Varying the Polarization of the Incident Wave:* This MS has a period $p = 3.36$ mm, ring resonator of size $R_1 = 3.12$ mm, $R_2 = 2.64$ mm, and width $w = 0.24$ mm. We calculate the MS response for both an x - and a y -polarized incident plane wave. Fig. 3(b) shows the MS response calculated by both the MoL and FEM solvers for both polarizations. The average absolute error is $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0211$ for the $|S_{21}|$ and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0101$ for the $|S_{11}|$ in the case of y -polarization, and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0888$ for the $|S_{21}|$ and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0593$ for the $|S_{11}|$ in the case of x -polarization. We observe a satisfactory agreement between the MoL and the FEM solvers on the S -parameters for both polarizations. Certain minor differences between the MoL and FEM responses may be partially attributed to

Fig. 3. (a) 2×1 MS supercell and (b) S -parameter comparison, between the extended MoL (M.) and FEM (F.), considering both an x - and y -polarized incident plane wave.

different meshes used in the MoL and the FEM; a square finite-difference grid for the MoL and a tetrahedral mesh in the FEM. The proposed MoL formulation is open to consider a non-uniform mesh, even by 2-D-triangular FEM, which may improve accuracy by locally refining the mesh on sharp metal edges and corners. The additional closely spaced metal elements with sharp edges and considerable coupling in the 2×1 supercell are also factors that contribute to the slightly increased mismatch compared with the 1×1 cell.

We consider $N_x = 56$ and $N_y = 28$ grid points along the x - and y -axes, with the total grid size being $56 \times 28 = 1568$. The DoFs used in the MoL formulation are $4 \times N_x \times N_y = 6272$, while approximately 3 946 610 are needed for the FEM. It takes about 80 s to compute the MS response at a single frequency using the MoL on the AMD processor and 99.8 s on the Intel processor. It takes about 24 min by the FEM solver on the AMD and 155 min on the Intel processor. We also note that the MoL is a prototype in-house MATLAB code, where the dense matrix operations utilize multi-threaded BLAS/LAPACK across cores. The FEM response is obtained by the commercial COMSOL Multiphysics solver.

We emphasize that changing the polarization of the incident plane wave only changes (20) and (21), which incurs minimal computational cost. To do this, for each frequency we save the total S -parameter matrix in terms of the amplitude coefficients \mathbf{c} (\mathbf{S}_c) (19) and calculate (20) and (21) for each polarization. The computation of (20) and (21) takes less than 1/40 of the total MoL execution time; hence, changing the polarization of the incident wave is very efficient. In contrast, the FEM response would have to be calculated as many times as the number of incident polarizations considered.

Fig. 4. S -parameter comparison, between the extended MoL (M.) and FEM (F.) for the 2×1 MS supercell varying the ring-resonator size R_2 .

2) *Varying the Ring-Resonator Dimensions:* We consider an MS supercell with a period $p = 2.88$ mm, ring resonator of size $R_1 = 2.64$ mm, and width $w = 0.24$ mm and vary the size of the second ring resonator between two values $R_2 = 2.16$ mm and $R_2 = 1.92$ mm. We calculate the MS response for both ring-resonator sizes, considering a y -polarized incident plane wave and compare the results to those obtained by the FEM in Fig. 4. Satisfactory agreement is observed for both resonator sizes. The absolute average error is $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0173$ and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0105$ for $|S_{21}|$ of $R_2 = 2.16$ mm and $R_2 = 1.92$ mm, and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0075$ and $E_a^{\text{avg}} = 0.0048$ for $|S_{11}|$, respectively.

As the two MSs are arranged on the same 2×1 substrate, we calculate the $ABCD$ matrix of the dielectric substrate and the eigenvalues and eigenvectors for the surrounding air domain only once for each frequency and store them. Then, we apply the SCDBC to the appropriate cells for each of the two MSs and form the total $ABCD$ matrix of each device, as described in Section II.

We consider $N_x = 48$ and $N_y = 24$ grid points along the x - and y -axes, with the total grid size being $48 \times 24 = 1152$. DoFs used in the MoL formulation are $4 \times N_x \times N_y = 4608$, while 2 885 074 are needed for the FEM. It takes about 37 s to compute the MS response at a single frequency using the MoL solver on the AMD processor and 41 s on the Intel processor. It takes about 12 min by the FEM solver on the AMD machine and 79 min on the Intel processor. The peak RAM is 70 GB for COMSOL Multiphysics FEM direct solver, by observing the maximum physical memory value, and only 0.3 GB for the MoL, as shown in MATLAB's profiler under peak memory.

We note that calculating the matrix exponential $\mathbf{T} = e^{\mathbf{A}_s(z'_1 - z'_2)}$ by MATLAB's `expm` function [21], [22] takes about half of the total MoL computation time per frequency. Calculating the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the air region (\mathbf{W}, \mathbf{V}) takes about 1/4 of the MoL calculation time per frequency. Hence, the main computational cost, about 3/4 of the total MoL execution time per frequency, is attributed to calculating the $ABCD$ matrix of the dielectric substrate and the eigenvalues and eigenvectors for the surrounding air domain. Therefore, in this case as well, the analysis of MS structures that share the same substrate can be significantly expedited compared with using the FEM, which would require

calculating the response of each different MS configuration independently.

IV. CONCLUSION

We presented an extended MoL formulation for the fast analysis and design of mmWave MS structures. We introduce the metal resonator patterns as an SCDBC, which greatly facilitates and expedites the synthesis process. The transfer matrices of each dielectric substrate are computed only once per frequency, which constitutes the primary computational cost. We show that although the FEM would require the simulation of the entire MS when changing the metal resonator pattern; in the proposed MoL formulation, we only change the BCs on the resonator layer and calculate the final transfer matrix. Additionally, we show that varying the polarization of the incident plane wave is very fast in the MoL formulation compared to the FEM. The benefits of our approach will be even more pronounced when synthesizing even more complex MS structures or aperiodic MSs. The MoL can be extended to curvilinear objects [13] or oblique incidence [12]. It may also be combined with gradient-based optimization approaches, such as the adjoint method, for fast optimization of MSs. Other semi-analytical methods, such as the rigorous coupled wave analysis (RCWA), have already been successfully combined with the adjoint method [23].

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